

KIDNEY ANATOMY, PATHOLOGY AND KIDNEY DISEASES: INFORMATION ABOUT NEPHRITIS

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Annotation. This article covers the kidney anatomy and nephritis disease and its primary symptoms in detail. Also, this article describes the types, stages and consequences of nephritis.

Key words: sclerosis, necrosis, channel, interstitial, pathogenesis, immunopathological, infiltration

In some patients, the disease becomes prolonged, the function of the tubules decreases, sclerosis foci, necrosis, SBE develop. Many authors called tubulointerstitial nephropathy damage to tubulointerstitial tissue. The frequency of IN in children has not been determined.

Pathogenesis of interstitial nephritis is based on immunopathological reactions or lymphohistocytic infiltration in interstitial tissues of the kidney.

1. The development of acute interstitial nephritis is caused by drugs, damage from toxins, damage to the basal membrane of tubules by viruses, formation of AG complexes (foreign AG and AG tubules in tubules), excess of components, leukocytes, and immune complexes in the damaged area.

2. It is important to synthesize autoantibodies against basal membrane oxides in the body. Oxyl and AT are found in the urine of patients with interstitial nephritis.

3. In many children, the increase of IgE can be determined by the fact that it has accumulated in large quantities in the perivascular infiltrates of the interstitial tissue. 4. In the pathogenesis of interstitial nephritis, a delayed type of hypersensitivity reaction may also be important.

5. Factors predisposing to the development of interstitial nephritis include: hereditary or increased defect of the phagocytic link.

6. Chronic interstitial nephritis often develops due to the accumulation of urates and oxalates in the interstitial tissue in hereditary nephropathies. These urates and oxalates affect the development of mononuclear infection, the release of inflammatory mediators from leukocytes, the activation of the kinin system and 12 factors, and the coagulation factor. As a result of inflammation and edema in the interstitial tissue of the renal brain cavity, the tubules of the renal blood vessels are pressed. This, in turn, makes it difficult for the blood circulation in the kidney to increase the pressure inside the tubules, and in severe cases, oligouria and azotemia develop.

7. Development of the inflammatory process in the canals leads to their dystrophy, necrosis, dysfunction - hypoisosthenuria, acidosis, polyuria and hypoglycemia. A.S. Rakhimov. Hospital Pediatrics. Tashkent. 2010. 189.

Kidneys are the main organs of the urinary system. They mainly work to filter the blood to remove waste and excess water. Waste and water are excreted as urine. The kidneys also reabsorb and return to the blood, containing amino acids, sugar, sodium, potassium and other useful substances. The kidneys filter about 200 liters of blood per day and produce about 2 liters of waste and extra fluid. This urine flows into the bladder through tubes called the urethra. The bladder stores urine until it leaves the body.

Kidneys are popularly described as bean-shaped and reddish in color. They are located in the middle of the spinal cord and are located on both sides of the spine. Each kidney is about 12 centimeters long and 6 centimeters wide. Blood is supplied to each kidney through an artery called the renal artery. Recycled blood is removed from the kidneys and returned to the circulation through blood vessels called renal vessels. Inside each kidney is a region called the renal medulla. Each medulla consists of structures called renal pyramids. Kidney pyramids consist of elongated parts of tube-like structures that collect blood vessels and filters. The regions of the medulla have a darker color than the outer

cortex of the kidney. The cortex also expands between regions of the medulla to form sections known as the renal columns. The renal pelvis is where the kidney collects urine and passes it to the ureters. N. Fayziyev. Regarding prevention. Tashkent. "Ziya", 2001. 34.

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